

Denseness of $J = \{A + BT : A, B \in M_k(\mathbb{Z})\}$ in the Space of all $k \times k$ real matrices, where T is a fixed $k \times k$ matrix with irrational entries

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Abstract- Several countable minimal dense subsets of \mathbb{R} are known to exist. An important example is the set $Z + Zq = \{a + bq : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, where q is an irrational number. In this paper, we establish an analogous result in the space of matrices $M_k(\mathbb{R})$. We prove that the set

$J = \{A + BT : A, B \in M_k(\mathbb{Z})\}$ is dense in $M_k(\mathbb{R})$ under the metric on $M_k(\mathbb{R})$ defined by

$$d(X, Y) = \|X - Y\|_p = \left(\sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq k} |X(i, j) - Y(i, j)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

Where T be a fixed matrix in $M_k(\mathbb{R})$ whose entries are irrational numbers.

Keywords: Dense sets, Space of matrices, Sequential convergence, Archimedean Property, Countability

1. Introduction

The study of dense subsets of \mathbb{R} under the usual metric has been a foundational topic in real analysis and number theory. It is well known that many dense subsets of \mathbb{R} exist under the usual metric. The set of all rational numbers \mathbb{Q} is a well-known example of a countable minimal dense subset of \mathbb{R} . Similarly, the set of all irrationals is also dense in \mathbb{R} , though uncountable. Beyond these classical examples, the set $Z + Zq = \{a + bq : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$, where q is irrational, plays a central role in the construction of countable dense subsets of \mathbb{R} . This set behaves similarly to \mathbb{Q} and forms a minimal dense subset of \mathbb{R} . Although several proofs exist for this result, here we present a sequential convergence proof that provides a constructive understanding of the denseness property. The proof uses a recursively defined sequence $(x_n) \subset Z + Zq$ converging to zero. Using this, we establish the denseness of $Z + Zq$ in \mathbb{R} . We then extend this idea to the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m , and further to the matrix space $M_k(\mathbb{R})$, the set of all $k \times k$ real matrices. We prove that $J = \{A + BT : A, B \in M_k(\mathbb{Z})\}$ is dense in $M_k(\mathbb{R})$ whenever T is a matrix with irrational entries. This result provides a natural higher-dimensional generalization of the classical integer-irrational denseness property.

2. Preliminaries

Archimedean Property 2.1. [3] If $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ with $x > 0$, then there exist a positive integer n such that $nx > y$

Inequality Lemma 2.2. If $a, b > 0$ and $a + b = k$ with $k > 0$, then $\min\{a, b\} \leq \frac{k}{2}$

Density Extension Lemma 2.3. Let A be a dense subset of \mathbb{R} , then any set B with $A \subset B \subset \mathbb{R}$ is also dense in \mathbb{R} .

3. Denseness of $Z + Zq$ via Sequential Convergence and its extension

Theorem 3.1: Let Z is the set of all integers, and q is a fixed irrational. Then the set $Z + Zq = \{a + bq : a, b \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ is dense in \mathbb{R} .

Proof: Let q be a fixed irrational number. We construct a strictly decreasing sequence (x_n) with $x_n \in Z + Zq, \forall n$ with $x_n \rightarrow 0$

Let $x_1 = q - [q]$, where $[q]$ denotes the greatest integer less than or equal to q

Clearly $0 < x_1 < 1$.

Let k_1 be the least positive integer such that $k_1 x_1 > 1$. Then

$$0 < (k_1 - 1) x_1 < 1 < k_1 x_1$$

By the Inequality Lemma, either $k_1 x_1 - 1$ or $1 - (k_1 - 1) x_1$ less than or equal to $\frac{x_1}{2}$. (Actually it is strictly less than, since q is irrational). Denote this smaller value by x_2

Then, $x_2 = \min\{k_1 x_1 - 1, 1 - (k_1 - 1) x_1\}$ and $0 < x_2 \leq \frac{x_1}{2} < x_1 < 1$. Also $x_2 \in Z + Zq$

Proceeding recursively, we define $x_{n+1} = \min\{k_n x_n - 1, 1 - (k_n - 1) x_n\}$ with k_n the least positive integer such that $k_n x_n > 1$.

Then, $0 < x_{n+1} \leq \frac{x_n}{2}$, so

$$0 < x_n \leq \frac{x_1}{2^{n-1}}$$

Implying $x_n \rightarrow 0$.

Hence, for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exist a positive integer N_0 such that

$$0 < x_n < \varepsilon, \text{ for all } n \geq N_0 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Next we will prove that the set $Z + Zq = \{a + bq: a, b \in Z\}$ is dense in R

Now let r be any real number, $\varepsilon > 0$ be given.

If $r \in Z + Zq$, there is nothing to prove.

So we assume $r \notin Z + Zq$. consider the case $r > 0$.

By the convergence of (x_n) , we can choose an x_k in the sequence such that $0 < x_k < r$ and $x_k < \varepsilon$.

That is, choose $x_k < \min\{r, \varepsilon\}$

Then there exist a positive integer M such that $Mx_k < r < (M + 1)x_k$.

Hence,

$$r < (M + 1)x_k = Mx_k + x_k < r + \varepsilon, \text{ and since } (M + 1)x_k \in Z + Zq$$

We have a point $(M + 1)x_k \in Z + Zq \cap B(r, \varepsilon)$, where $B(r, \varepsilon)$ denotes the ε -neighbourhood of r

For $r < 0$, take $r = -s$ with $s > 0$, and $\varepsilon > 0$ be given.

Then by the above result, we can find a $y \in Z + Zq$ such that

$$s < y < s + \varepsilon$$

Then

$$-s - \varepsilon < -y < -s$$

$$\text{That is, } r - \varepsilon < -y < r \text{ and } -y \in Z + Zq$$

$$\Rightarrow -y \in B(r, \varepsilon), \text{ with } -y \in Z + Zq$$

This shows that for any real r and an $\varepsilon > 0$, the ball $B(r, \varepsilon)$ contains a point of $Z + Zq$

Thus $Z + Zq$ dense in R .

Theorem.3.2. Let $q_1, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_k$ be distinct irrationals. Then the set

Then the set $A = \{a + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i q_i : a, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k \in Z\}$ is dense in R

Proof: $Z + Zq_1 = \{a + bq_1 : a, b \in Z\}$ is dense in R and $Z + Zq_1 \subset A \subset R$, the result follows from the Density Extension Lemma

Theorem.3.3. Let $q = (q_1, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_m) \in R^m$ with $q_1, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_m$ are fixed irrationals. Then

$Z^m + Z^m q = \{(a_1 + b_1 q_1, a_2 + b_2 q_2, \dots, a_m + b_m q_m) : a_1, a_2, \dots, a_m, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m \in Z\}$ is dense in R^m under the metric

$$\|x - y\|_p = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m |x_i - y_i|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

Proof: Let $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) \in R^m$.

For each co-ordinate $x_k \in R$, by the above theorem there exist sequence $(a_n(k) + b_n(k)q_k)$ in $Z + Zq_k$ such that

$$a_n(k) + b_n(k)q_k \rightarrow x_k$$

Hence,

$$(a_n(1) + b_n(1)q_1, a_n(2) + b_n(2)q_2, \dots, a_n(m) + b_n(m)q_m) \rightarrow (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$$

That is $a_n + b_n q \rightarrow x$, where $a_n = (a_n(1), a_n(2), \dots, a_n(m))$, $b_n = (b_n(1), b_n(2), \dots, b_n(m)) \in R^m$. This shows that $Z^m + Z^m q$ is dense in R^m under the metric

$$d(x, y) = \|x - y\|_p = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m |x_i - y_i|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

4. Extension to Space of Matrices

Theorem.4.1. Let $T \in M_k(I)$ be fixed, where I is the set of all irrationals. Then for any $X \in M_k(R)$, there exist sequences $(A_n), (B_n)$ with $A_n, B_n \in M_k(Z)$ such that $A_n + B_n T \rightarrow X$ under the metric on $M_k(R)$ defined by

$$d(X, Y) = \|X - Y\|_p = \left(\sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq k} |X(i, j) - Y(i, j)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

Hence the set $J = \{A + BT : A, B \in M_k(Z)\}$ is dense in $M_k(R)$. This set is also a countable dense subset of $M_k(R)$

Proof: Let $X = [X(i, j)] \in M_k(R)$ and $T = [T(i, j)]$

We have the set $A = \{a + \sum_{m=1}^k a_m q_m : a, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k \in Z\}$, where $q_1, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_k$ are fixed irrationals, is dense in R

That is, for each entry $X(i, j)$ of X , there exist sequences $(A_n(i, j)), (B_n(i, j))$ with entries in Z such that

$$C_n(i, j) = A_n(i, j) + \sum_{m=1}^k B_n(i, m)T(m, j) \rightarrow X(i, j)$$

That is, for each pair (i, j) and a given $\varepsilon > 0$, there exist a positive integer N such that

$$|A_n(i, j) + \sum_{m=1}^k B_n(i, m)T(m, j) - X(i, j)| < \frac{\varepsilon}{k^2}, \text{ for every } n \geq N \dots (1)$$

Take the matrices $A_n = [A_n(i, j)]$, $B_n = [B_n(i, j)]$. Then, $A_n + B_nT = [C_n(i, j)]$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \| (A_n + B_nT) - X \|_p &= \left(\sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq k} |C_n(i, j) - X(i, j)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &< \left(\sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq k} \left| \frac{\varepsilon}{k^2} \right|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \frac{\varepsilon}{k^2} \cdot k^2 = \varepsilon, \text{ for every } n \geq N. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the sequence $(A_n + B_nT)$ converges to X , proving that J is dense in $M_k(R)$. ■

5. Conclusions: We established the denseness of the set $Z + Zq$ via a sequential convergence argument. The result was extended to R^m and further to the space of matrices $M_k(R)$. The construction shows that the set $J = \{A + BT : A, B \in M_k(Z)\}$ is a countable minimal dense subset of $M_k(R)$ under the p -norm metric.

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